

In vitro antifungal activity of some new triazole compounds

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Abstract : In the present study, the derivatives of 1,2,4-triazoles were synthesized and tested for antifungal activity against *Candida tropicalis* ATCC-4563, *Candida albicans* ATCC-2091, *Cryptococcus neoformans* ATCC-34664, *Trichosporon beigeli* NCIM-3404 and *Aspergillus flavus* NCIM-538 by disc diffusion method. 1,2,4-Triazoles were obtained by cyclization of the potassium salt of substituted dithiocarbazine acid with hydrazine hydrate. The new synthesized compounds were characterized using IR, ¹H NMR spectral data and Mass spectrometry together with elemental analysis. The inhibitory effect of the newly synthesized triazole compounds was compared to the standard antifungal agents. Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined for those compounds which could inhibit all the tested fungal strains with maximum inhibition zone.

Keywords : 1,2,4-Triazoles, cyclization, antifungal activity, MIC.

Introduction

Fungal cells are complex organisms that share many biochemical targets with other eukaryotic cells. Therefore, agents that interact with fungal targets not found in eukaryotic cells are needed. The fungal cell wall is a unique organelle that fulfills the criteria for selective toxicity. Fungal cell wall differs greatly from bacterial cell wall. Therefore, fungi are unaffected by antibacterial cell wall inhibitors. A literature survey shows that azoles antifungal agents are the largest class of synthetic antimycotics¹⁻³ which exhibit high level of activity, application flexibility, crop tolerance and low levels of toxicity to mammals.

In the literature, biological activities of triazoles are well documented⁴⁻¹⁰. This class of compounds are known to exhibit antifungal agents¹¹⁻¹⁴, anti-inflammatory¹⁵⁻¹⁷, antiviral^{18,19}, analgesic^{20,21}, antimicrobial²²⁻²⁴, anticonvulsant²⁵ and antidepressant activity^{26,27}. Thus, taking this in to the view, a series of 1,2,4-triazole derivatives have synthesized and extensively tested for their antifungal activity.

Material and methods :

In the first part, synthesis of triazole and its deriva-

tives is given and in the second part their antifungal activity and MIC is given.

Part-I :

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by TLC. The IR spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu FTIR 8400 series and ¹H spectra on Bruker AC-300 MHz (DMSO) using TMS as an internal standard (Chemical shift are expressed in δ ppm). Precipitated potassium dithiocarbazine was collected by filtration, washed with ether and dried. The potassium salt obtained in quantitative yield was used directly without further purification.

The following compounds have been synthesized .

- (1) 5-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-4-(4-methylphenyl)-4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol.
- (2) 4,5-Bis(4-methoxyphenyl)-4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol
- (3) 4-(4-Chlorophenyl)-5-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol.
- (4) 5-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-4-(2-nitrophenyl)-4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol.
- (5) 5-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-4-(3-nitrophenyl)-4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol.

(6) 4-(2,5-Dimethylphenyl)-5-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol.

(7) 4-(2,3-Dichlorophenyl)-5-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol.

(8) 5-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-4-(2-methylphenyl)-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol.

(9) 4-(3-Chloro-4-fluorophenyl)-5-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol.

(10) 4-(2-Methoxyphenyl)-5-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol.

Synthesis of 3-mercapto-4-n-aryl-5-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1,2,4-triazoles :

(1) *Synthesis of ester :*

p-Methoxy benzoic acid in 25 ml methanol and 1 ml of conc. sulfuric acid was refluxed for 6 h and poured into ice. The product was isolated and treated with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution.

(2) *Synthesis of hydrazide :*

An equimolar mixture of ester and hydrazine hydrate was heated for 10 h and poured in to ice. The product was isolated and crystallized from ethyl alcohol.

(3) *Synthesis of potassium salt :*

A mixture of hydrazide, KOH and CS₂ in methanol was stirred for 12 h and poured into ice. The product was isolated from diethyl ether.

(4) *Synthesis of 5-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4-(4-methylphenyl)-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol :*

A mixture of potassium salt and *p*-toluidine was heated up to evolution of H₂S gas. DMF was added to this mixture and contents were poured into ice. The crude product was filtered and crystallized from ethyl alcohol. Yield 65%, m.p. 190 °C.

Similarly other 4-aryl triazoles were synthesized. The reaction scheme is given in Scheme 1.

Part-II :

Assay for antifungal activity :

To evaluate the antifungal activity, sterile agar plates were used according to the disc diffusion assay²⁸. Activated cultures of fungal strains *Candida tropicalis* ATCC-4563, *Candida albicans* ATCC-2091, *Cryptococcus neoformans* ATCC-34664, *Trichosporon beigeli* NCIM-3404 and *Aspergillus flavus* NCIM-538 in Sabouraud's

broth were adjusted to 1×10^8 cfu/m as per Mcfarland standard. 100 μ L of the inoculum was introduced to molten sabouraud dextrose agar and poured in the sterile Petri plates. Sterile filter paper discs (7.0 mm diameter) were impregnated with 500 μ g/disc of the test compounds dissolved in 100% DMSO (dimethylsulphoxide) and dried. The discs were placed on fungal-seeded plates and incubated at 28 °C for 48 h. Discs Impregnated with only 100% DMSO served as the negative control. As a positive control, fluconazole and ketoconazole were used. Following an incubation period of 48 h, plates were removed from the incubator and antifungal activity was evaluated by measuring zones of inhibition of fungal growth. Clear zones within which fungal growth was absent were measured and recorded as the diameter (mm) of complete growth-inhibition. The whole experiment was performed three times to minimize the error.

Results and discussion

The new synthesized triazole compounds were characterized using IR, ¹H NMR spectral data and Mass spectrometry. Physical constants of synthesized compounds are shown in Table 1. The inhibition zones of all the ten triazole compounds evaluated against the five medically important fungal strains is shown in Table 2. Further, the minimum inhibitory concentration of most potent compounds was determined (Table 3).

IR spectral data :

Comps.	S-H	C=C	Ar-H	N-N
HASD-1	1090	1514	3010	1610
HASD-2	1099	1504	3011	1609
HASD-3	1100	1523	3008	1614
HASD-4	1089	1542	3009	1608
HASD-5	1095	1526	3019	1608
HASD-6	1120	1513	3010	1613
HASD-7	1099	1508	3011	1612
HASD-8	1100	1545	3012	1606
HASD-9	1112	1542	3010	1609
HASD-10	1112	1517	3018	1611

¹H NMR spectral data (δ ppm) :

(HASD-1) : 2.43 (3H-CH₃), 3.78 (3H-OCH₃), 6.77 (2H-Ar-Haa'), 7.16 (2H-Ar-Hdd'), 7.22 (4H-Ar-H), 11.6

Scheme 1

Table 1. Physical constants of synthesized compounds

Sl. no.	R ₁	Compound code	Molecular weight (g)	Molecular formula	R _f * value	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)
1.	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	HASD-1	297.38	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ ON ₃ S	0.63	190	66
2.	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	HASD-2	313.38	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ S	0.59	196	79
3.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	HASD-3	317.80	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ OCIN ₃ S	0.78	160	81
4.	2-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	HASD-4	328.35	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₄ S	0.65	240	59
5.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	HASD-5	328.35	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₄ S	0.45	260	77
6.	2,4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	HASD-6	311.40	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ ON ₃ S	0.51	162	74
7.	2,3-Cl-C ₆ H ₃	HASD-7	352.24	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ OCIN ₃ S	0.70	169	83
8.	2-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	HASD-8	297.38	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ ON ₃ S	0.66	166	78
9.	3-Cl-4-F-C ₆ H ₃	HASD-9	335.79	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ OCIFN ₃ S	0.61	135	64
10.	2-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	HASD-10	313.38	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ S	0.55	110	68

Acetone : benzene = 0.5 : 9.5 for 1, 2, 5, 6, 7 and 9.

Methanol : hexane = 3 : 7 for 3, 4, 8 and 10.

Table 2. Antifungal activity of some triazole compounds

Compound code	Zone of inhibition (mm) ^a				
	<i>Ct</i>	<i>Ca</i>	<i>Cn</i>	<i>Tb</i>	<i>Af</i>
HASD-1	10	-	9	14	14
HASD-2	13	16	17	15	23
HASD-3	-	12	-	-	-
HASD-4	12	9	12	10	12
HASD-5	11.5	-	15	16	14
HASD-6	15	16	28	23	27
HASD-7	11	15	28	18	21
HASD-8	12	17	30	16	20
HASD-9	10	10	-	12	15
HASD-10	9	-	-	-	10
Fu ^b	-	17	22	28	22
Kt ^c	-	14	19	18	32

^aMean values of zone diameter is taken; - : no activity.

Ct : *Candida tropicalis* ATCC-4563; *Ca* : *Candida albicans* ATCC-2091; *Cn* : *Cryptococcus neoformans* ATCC-34664; *Tb* : *Trichosporon beigeli* NCIM-3404; *Af* : *Aspergillus flavus* NCIM-538.

^bFluconazole (10 mcg/disc).

^cKetoconazole (10 mcg/disc).

Table 3. Determination of the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)

Compound	MIC (µg/disc)				
	<i>Ct</i>	<i>Ca</i>	<i>Cn</i>	<i>Tb</i>	<i>Af</i>
HASD-2	50	50	100	50	25
HASD-6	25	12.5	12.5	50	25
HASD-7	25	25	50	25	25
HASD-8	25	6.25	6.25	25	50

(1H-SH); (HASD-2) : 3.78 (6H-2OCH₃), 6.63 (4H-Ar-Haa'), 6.94 (2H-Ar-Hbb'), 6.96 (2H-Ar-dd'), 11.56 (1H-SH); (HASD-3) : 3.75 (3H-OCH₃), 6.65 (2H-Ar-Haa'), 7.07 (2H-Ar-H), 7.32 (2H-Ar-dd'), 7.42 (1H-Ar-Hbb'), 11.43 (1H-SH); (HASD-4) : 3.67 (3H-OCH₃), 6.63 (2H-Ar-Haa'), 7.25 (2H-Ar-Hbb'), 7.54 (2H-Ar-H), 8.0 (1H-Ar-H), 11.52 (1H-SH); (HASD-5) : 3.65 (3H-OCH₃), 6.50 (2H-Ar-Haa'), 7.31 (2H-Ar-Hbb'), 7.62 (2H-Ar-H), 8.12 (2H-Ar-H), 11.42 (1H-SH); (HASD-6) : 3.61 (3H-OCH₃), 2.34 (3H-CH₃), 2.40 (3H-CH₃), 6.84 (2H-Ar-Haa'), 7.43 (2H-Ar-Hbb'), 7.10 (3H-Ar-Hdd'), 11.61 (1H-SH); (HASD-7) : 3.62 (3H-OCH₃), 6.40 (2H-Ar-Haa'), 7.54 (2H-Ar-Hbb'), 7.23 (3H-Ar-H), 11.63 (1H-SH); (HASD-8) : 3.71 (3H-OCH₃), 2.20 (3H-CH₃), 6.65 (2H-Ar-Haa'), 6.93 (3H-Ar-H), 7.44 (2H-Ar-Hbb'), 11.57 (1H-

SH); (HASD-9) : 3.75 (3H-OCH₃), 6.67 (2H-Ar-Haa'), 6.71 (1H-Ar-H), 7.37 (4H-Ar-H), 11.14 (1H-SH); (HASD-10) : 3.62 (3H-OCH₃), 6.67 (2H-Ar-Haa'), 7.23 (2H-Ar-H), 7.40 (2H-Ar-H), 11.64 (1H-SH); MS : (HASD-1) *m/z* 136, 154, 165, 224, 284, 298.

Amongst all the triazole compounds, maximum antifungal activity was shown by HASD-6 and it could inhibit to a great extent all the 5 fungal strains studied.

Amongst the five strains, *Cryptococcus neoformans* was the most susceptible strain for HASD-6. Similar activity was shown by HASD-7 and HASD-8 followed by HASD-2 and HASD-4. All the five compounds inhibited *Cryptococcus neoformans* to a great extent and minimum activity was against *Candida tropicalis*. HASD-1 and HASD-5 could not inhibit *Candida albicans* while HASD-3 could inhibit only *Candida albicans*. HASD-9, on the other hand, could not inhibit *Cryptococcus neoformans* while HASD-10 showed slight inhibitory activity against *Candida tropicalis* and mould *Aspergillus flavus*. This differential activity may be because of the differences in the structure of the compound. In all the ten compounds the main basic moiety is triazole to which different side chains are attached. In HASD-1 it is 4-methyl aniline, in HASD-2 it is 4-methoxy aniline, in HASD-3 it is 4-chloro aniline, in HASD-4 it is 2-nitro aniline, in HASD-5 it is 3-nitro aniline, in HASD-6 it is 2,4-dimethyl aniline, in HASD-7 it is 2,3-dichloro aniline, in HASD-8 it is 2-methyl aniline, in HASD-9 it is 3-chloro, 4-fluoro aniline and in HASD-10, it is 2-methoxy aniline. It is very clear from the present results that the attached group clearly affects the antifungal activity and there is a distinct relationship between structure and antifungal activity as already reported by the authors in their earlier work on antibacterial activity²⁹. HASD-6 was the most potent antifungal compound i.e. 2,4-dimethyl aniline. It is also apparent from the present work, that not only a particular group but its attachment to the central moiety is also important. For example, 4-methoxy aniline (HASD-2) showed good antifungal activity but the same methoxy group as 2-methoxy aniline (HASD-10), could not show the antifungal effect. Antifungal activity stems from the presence of an aromatic five-member heterocyclic moiety that is triazole. Triazoles inhibit the cytochrome P450 enzyme 14-demethylase, thus disrupting synthesis of ergosterol in the fungal cell membrane. Furthermore, when HASD-2, HASD-6, HASD-7 and HASD-8 further subjected to the evaluation of minimum inhibitory concen-

tration (MIC), the values ranged between 6.5–100 μg (Table 3).

From the antifungal screening, it was found that the compounds screened showed significant activity, some equipotent and some are even more potent than the standard drug when compared.

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